

Most of the compounds were found active against both the strains of *M. tuberculosis* at higher concentrations (100 and 150 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). Antitubercular activity of the compounds having hydrogen atom at the fifth position of thiazolidinone ring is nearly the same as the compounds having methyl group at the same position. Most of the compounds are more active against the strain H₃₇R_v than the strain isolated from the sputum of pulmonary tuberculosis patient.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Bhavnagar University for facilities and for a Research Scholarship to one of them (M.D.J.), to the Ministry of Higher Education, Government of Gujarat, for a Research Scholarship to the other (M.K.J.) and to Dr. S. B. Trivedi, Ex-Director, Tuberculosis Research Centre, Amargadh, for antimicrobial screening.

References

- S. N. GOLUBOVA, *Ukr. Biokhim. Zh.*, 1953, **25**, 325; G. SATZINGER, US Pat. 3 072 670/1963 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, **58**, 12569); K. ENRICO, *Gazz. Chem. Ital.*, 1949, **79**, 621; M. RAI, B. S. DHIR and P. S. KALSI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 705; M. P. DAVE, J. M. PATEL, N. A. LANGALIA and K. A. THAKER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 320; H. D. TROUTMANN and L. M. LONG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3436.
- M. BUCKELL and J. D. RICHARDSON, *Br. J. Ind. Med.*, 1950, **7**, 131.
- J. P. JOUIN and BUU-HOI, *Ann. Inst. Pasteur*, 1946, **72**, 580.
- K. E. STAHL and F. JUNG, *Naunyn-Schmiedbergs, Arch Exptl. Pethol. Pharmacol*, 1953, **220**, 503.
- W. M. M. KIRBI and A. W. BAUER, *Am. J. Clin. Pathol.*, 1966, **45**, 493.
- G. CANETTI, *Bull. Wld. Health Org.*, 1963, **29**, 565.

Biologically Active Thiazolidinone. Part-II. Synthesis and Fungitoxicities of isolated and fused Thiazolidinones derived from Thiosemicarbazones

Z. EL-GENDY, R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN*, M. M. FAWZY and M. B. MAHMOUD**

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Education, Ain Shams University, Roxy, Cairo, AR Egypt

Manuscript received 24 April 1990, accepted 12 October 1990

In continuation to the work on thiazolidinones¹, we report here the synthesis and reactions of some new thiazolidinones as well as fungitoxic activity of the new compounds against some fungi. The sequence of reactions leading to the formation of the title compounds is depicted in Schemes 1 and 2.

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) $\text{ClCH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}/\text{EtOH}/\text{NaOAc}$, (ii) $\text{SHCH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}/\text{dry C}_6\text{H}_6$, (iii) K-ferricyanide/NaOH, (iv) $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NCS}/\text{DMF}$, and (v) concentrated H_2SO_4 .

Scheme 2

A number of thiosemicarbazones (1a-i) and the bis-compound (14) have been prepared by the condensation of thiosemicarbazide with aromatic aldehydes.

** Plant Protection Department, Faculty of Agriculture, El Azhar University, Cairo, Egypt.

Condensation of **1a-d** with chloroacetic acid afforded thiazolidin-4-ones (**2a-c**) which on reaction with mercaptoacetic acid yielded 2-(4-oxothiazolidin-3-ylamino)- Δ^2 -thiazolin-4-ones (**3a, b**). The compounds **3a, b** underwent cyclodehydration with concentrated H_2SO_4 to furnish bisthiazolo[3,4-*b*:3',2'-*d*] [1,2,4]triazol-8(3*H*,7*H*)one (**5**). The compounds **3a, b** were also obtained via an alternative route which involving condensation of mercaptoacetic acid to **1c, d** followed by the condensation **4** with chloroacetic acid.

Oxidative cyclisation of **2** using potassium ferricyanide³ led to the direct formation of 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (**6**). The presence of NH_2 group in **6** was established by addition of allyl thioisocyanate to give 1,3-disubstituted-thiourea (**7**) (Scheme 1). On the other hand, alkylation of **1e-i** with 3-chloro-5,6-diphenyl-1,2,4-triazino (**8**)⁴ in the presence of DMF (the isomeric structure **9A** or **10** may be formed, which was established by its reaction with chloroacetic acid), 2,3-disubstituted-thiazolidin-4-one (**11**) was isolated and not another **9B** and this is due to the absence of carboxylic group properties. Finally, addition of HCN to compound **1** gave the 1-substituted-thiosemicarbazide (**12**) which on acidic hydrolysis with concentrated HCl ⁵ led to the direct formation of 3-thioxo-6-substituted-hexahydro-1,2,4-triazin-5-one (**13**).

Bisthiosemicarbazone (**14**) also on treatment with potassium ferricyanide in aqueous NaOH gave the amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole derivative (**15**) (Scheme 2).

Antifungal activity: The *in vitro* antifungal activity of the compounds was tested by screening against *Penicillium italicum*, *P. digitatum*, *Botrytis cinerea* and *Aspergillus niger* as plant pathogenic fungi. DMF was used to make desired concentrations of the compounds, and sterile potato dextrose agar (PDA) cultures were used. The culture plates were inoculated with 4 mm dia disc of inoculum of each fungus removed from a 7-day old culture. Fungitoxicity was evaluated according to the ED_{50} values.

The *in vivo* fungitoxic activity of the compounds was tested against *P. digitatum* development on lime fruits (*Citrus aurantifolia*, Christm Swingle). The compounds were evaluated as pre- or post-inoculation and their antispore activity⁶.

Results and Discussion

The results indicate that substituted-thiosemicarbazones (**1a-i**) were inactive (except **1c, 1g**), while **2a** enhanced the fungitoxic property than **2b**. The most active compound was **3a** and *P. digitatum* was the most affected fungus by this compound. It was found that the compounds did not prevent or reduce the development of the disease either applied pre- or post-inoculation treatment, except compound **3a**. On the other hand, at high concentration these compounds prevented completely the sporulation of the fungus on the fruit surface. This confirmed that

these compounds had low antifungal activity except compound **3a**, which gave good reduction of the decay of lime fruits and excellent control of the fungal sporulation on decayed fruits. Regarding to the structure activity relationship, the results indicate that the dihydroxyphenyl derivative (**1a**) was more active than introduction of methoxy group to the phenyl ring (**1b**). This result agreed with Addy and Mitru⁷. The results also show that the introduction of chloro or nitro atoms in *para*-position of phenyl ring caused enhanced fungitoxicity.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. Uv spectra (DMF) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 550-S spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Pye-Unicam SP 1100 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra ($DMSO-d_6$) on a EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Compound **8** was prepared by the reported procedure⁴.

General method for preparation of thiosemicarbazones (1a-i): An equimolar mixture of aldehyde and thiosemicarbazide (in hot water) in ethanol was refluxed for 1 h to yield orange yellow crystals (Table 1): ν_{max} **1d** 3 450 (NH_2), 3 300 (NH), 3 020 (CH aromatic), 1 620 (def. NH_2), 1 550 (C=N),

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (1-15)*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M. p. °C	Mol. formula
1a	75	240	$C_8H_9N_3SO_2$
1b	78	190	$C_9H_{11}N_3SO_2$
1c	80	248	$C_8H_7N_3SCl_2$
1d	85	230	$C_8H_7N_3SCl_2$
1e	76	250	$C_8H_8N_4SO_2$
1f	80	290	$C_8H_8N_4SO_2$
1g	75	255	$C_8H_8N_4SO_2$
1h	60	147	$C_6H_7N_3SO$
1i	55	188	$C_7H_8N_4S$
2a	60	290	$C_{10}H_7N_3SCl_2O$
2b	65	205	$C_{10}H_7N_3SCl_2O$
3a	75	230	$C_{12}H_9N_3S_2Cl_2O_2$
3b	60	240	$C_{12}H_9N_3S_2Cl_2O_2$
4a	60	200	$C_{10}H_9N_3S_2Cl_2O$
4b	70	235	$C_{10}H_9N_3S_2Cl_2O$
5	60	290	$C_{12}H_7N_3S_2Cl_2O$
6a	60	250	$C_8H_7N_3SO_2$
6b	65	289	$C_8H_8N_3SCl_2$
7	60	160	$C_{12}H_{12}N_4S_2O_2$
10a	65	220	$C_{23}H_{17}N_7SO_2$
10b	60	290	$C_{23}H_{17}N_7SO_2$
10c	67	247	$C_{23}H_{17}N_7SO_2$
10d	70	260	$C_{21}H_{16}N_6SO_2$
10e	68	220	$C_{22}H_{17}N_7S$
11a	55	130	$C_{25}H_{17}N_7SO_2$
11b	65	240	$C_{25}H_{17}N_7SO_2$
11c	50	197	$C_{25}H_{17}N_7SO_2$
11d	65	230	$C_{25}H_{16}N_6SO_2$
11e	66	163	$C_{24}H_{17}N_7SO$
12a	55	290	$C_{10}H_{12}N_4SO_2$
13	75	ab. 300	$C_{10}H_{11}N_3SO_2$
14	60	170	$C_{10}H_{12}N_6S_2$
15	65	280	$C_{10}H_8N_6S_2$

*Elemental analyses for all compounds were found satisfactory.

1 380 (NCSH), 1 190–1 170 (C=S), 950, 890, 840 (substituted-phenyl) and 820–768 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); ν_{max} 370, 340 and 300 nm.

Reaction of 1 with monochloroacetic acid. (i) Formation of 2a–c: An equimolar mixture of an aldehyde thiosemicarbazones (**1b, c, d**), monochloroacetic acid and fused sodium acetate in ethanol was refluxed for 4 h. Alcohol was then distilled off and the residue washed with hot water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to give **2a–c** (Table 1): ν_{max} **2c** 3 300 (NH), 3 050 (CH aromatic), 2 800 (CH aliphatic), 1 770–1 730 (C=O), 1 660–1 640 (CONH), 1 590 (C=N), 1 440 (def. CH_2), 1 340 (NCS), 1 240 (–N–N=C cyclic), 1 040 (C–S in ring), 960, 890, 840 (substituted-phenyl) and 740–710 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); λ_{max} **2c** 325, 315, 300, 285, 210 and 200 nm; δ **2c** 3.3 (2H, CH_2), 3.9 (1H, CH=), 7.5–7.7 (3H, ArH) and 8.6 (1H, NH).

(ii) Formation of 4a–b: To a well-stirred solution of **1c, d** (0.01 mol) in dry benzene was added mercaptoacetic acid (0.02 mol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h on a water-bath. On cooling and stirring, the resulting precipitate was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to give **4a, b** (Table 1): ν_{max} **4b** 3 430 (NH_2), 3 300 (NH), 3 020 (CH aromatic), 2 810 (CH aliphatic), 1 750–1 702 (C=O), 1 610 (def. NH_2), 1 440 (def. CH_2), 1 380 (NCS), 1 070 (C–S), 940, 880, 840 (substituted-phenyl), 710 and 630 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); δ **4b** 2.2 (2H, CH_2), 3.6 (1H, CH), 7.7–7.4 (3H, ArH), 8.4 (1H, NH) and 11.9 (2H, NH_2).

Formation of 3: The method is similar to the formation of **2** and **4**; m.p. and m.m.p. gave no depression.

Acidic cyclisation of 3. Formation of 5: Compounds **3a, b** (0.01 mol) were treated dropwise with concentrated H_2SO_4 (5 ml) and the mixture was stirred under cooling for 1 h and then water added. On basification with aqueous ammonia solution, the resulting solid was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from ethanol to give **5a, b** (Table 1).

Oxidative cyclisation of 1a, d. Formation of 4a, b: A mixture of thiosemicarbazones **1a, d** in ethanol (95%, 50 ml) and NaOH solution in a little water was warmed on a water-bath and a solution of potassium ferricyanide (5%) added to it dropwise until precipitation took place. The contents were warmed for 5 min, cooled and filtered. The solid so obtained was washed with hot water to remove excess $\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ and crystallised (Table 1): ν_{max} **6b** 3 420 (NH_2), 3 300 (NH=C), 3 170 (NH cyclic), 3 020 (CH aromatic), 2 100–2 050 (NCS triadiazole), 1 640–1 620 (def. NH_2), 1 600, 1 550 (C=N), 1 380 (NCSN cyclic), 1 050 (C–S–C), 940, 890, 840 (substituted-phenyl) and 770–720 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); δ **6b** 6.8–7.3 (3H, ArH), 8.3 (1H, NH acyclic) and 9.5 (2H, NH cyclic).

1,3-Disubstitutedthiourea (7): An equimolar mixture of **4a** and allyl thioisocyanate in DMF (100

ml) was refluxed for 1 h, cooled and diluted with cold water. The solid obtained was crystallised (Table 1); δ 2.5 (2H, CH_2), 3.6 (1H, =CH), 7.3–7.7 (3H, ArH), 8.4–8.6 (1H, NH) and 11.8 (1H, OH phenolic).

Alkylation of 1e–i with 3-chloro-5,6-diphenyl-1,2,4-triazine (8). Formation of 10a–e: A solution of **1** (0.01 mol) and **8** (0.01 mol) in DMF (100 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. On cooling the reaction mixture was acidified with dilute HCl and the solid products was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (Table 1); ν_{max} 3 300–3 100 (NH), 2 700 (SH), 1 580 (C=N), 900 and 865 cm^{-1} (substituted-phenyl).

Reaction of 10e–i with monochloroacetic acid. Formation of 11a–e: The method was similar to the formation of compound **2** (Table 1).

Addition of HCN to thiosemicarbazone (1). Formation of 12: A mixture of thiosemicarbazone (**1b**; 0.01 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) and KCN (0.02 mol) in cold water (10 ml) and a few drops of piperidine was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h. On cooling and dilution the resultant solid was crystallised from ethanol (Table 1); ν_{max} **12b** 3 350–3 150 (NH_2 , NH), 2 235 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) and 1 175 cm^{-1} (C=S).

Acidic cyclisation of 12. Formation of 13: A suspension of **12** in concentrated HCl (100 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The solid obtained after cooling was filtered and washed with cold water and crystallised from CCl_4 (Table 1).

Bisthiosemicarbazone 14: A mixture of thiosemicarbazide (0.02 mol) in hot water, and phthaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 15 min. The solid obtained on cooling was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Oxidative cyclisation of 14. Formation of 15: The method was similar to the formation of **6** (Table 1).

References

1. R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN, *Pak. J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1987, **30**, 7, 490, 1989, **32**, 4, 240, R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN, Z. EL-GENDY and M. B. MAHMOUD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 61
2. H. SINGH, L. D. S. YADAV and A. K. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 147
3. H. K. SHUKLA, N. C. DESAI, R. R. ASTIK and K. A. THAKER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 168
4. P. V. LAAKSO, R. ROBINSON and H. P. VANDREWALA, *Tetrahedron*, 1957, **1**, 103.
5. L. C. MARCH, K. J. WASTI and M. MADELEME, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, **13**, 90120.
6. Y. GUTTER, *Plant Dis. Rep.*, 1970, **54**, 327. P. L. HARDING, *Plant Dis. Rep.*, 1978, **62**, 679.
7. S. K. ADDY and G. N. MITRA, *Phytopathology*, 1966, **56**, 485.